

SDS-PAGE gel assessing purity of BLM proteins (Figure S1)

Nuclease test of BLM proteins (Figure S1)

EMSA (Figure 3)

WT BLM, ssDNA

WT BLM, G4-DNA

WT BLM, dsDNA

BLM P868L, ssDNA

BLM P868L, G4DNA

BLM P868L, dsDNA

EMSA (Figure 3)

BLM G1120R, ssDNA

BLM G1120R, G4DNA

BLM G1120R, dsDNA

BLM K869A K870A, ssDNA

BLM K869A K870A, G4-DNA

BLM K869A K870A, dsDNA

Helicase Assays (Figure 4)

WT BLM, dsDNA

WT BLM, G4-dsDNA

BLM P868L, dsDNA

BLM P868L, G4-dsDNA

BLM G1120R, dsDNA

BLM G1120R, G4-dsDNA

Helicase Assays (Figure 4)

BLM K869A K870A, dsDNA

BLM K869A K870A, G4-dsDNA

